

Research Article

Evaluation of Human Capacity Development in Ondo State Building
Construction Industry

Francis Bamidele and Juliet Ifeoma Olatunde
The School of Postgraduate Studies, City University, Cambodia

Abstract

Human capacity development Strategies are the backbone of success in every organization. It was observed that the building industry has been plagued with collapse of buildings with resultant calamities in the recent times. The research focused on the evaluation of human capacity development in Ondo state building construction industry. The primary objectives of this study are: To assess the human capacity development approach used to develop the building construction staff in the study area; To examine the challenges faced by the Ondo state construction industry; To identify the human capacity development method preferred by the professionals. The design of the study follows the pattern of a survey research. Data was collected both from primary and secondary sources. A set of questionnaire was prepared specifically for the professionals and the contractors in the study area. In making the findings of this research possible, ninety-Eight (98) copies of questionnaire were administered, and the total number of ninety-two (92) copies were retrieved, 93.9% were used for the analysis. The data collected was analyzed using one-way Anova. The findings shows that, the level of human capacity development in the construction industry in Ondo State was very low (40%). It also shows that the human capacity development variables have direct effect on output of building construction industry. From the study it was recommended that formulation of human capacity policy should be adopted. Also provisions in terms of fund and personnel should be made available for regular training, while training should be carried out constantly for the professionals and contractors in the ministries to achieve desired output of building construction. In conclusion, the ministries should formulate a forward looking plan to ensure that necessary human efforts are achieved in making it possible for the survival and growth of the organization which will invariably help in developing the employees.

Keywords: construction industry, Ondo State, contractors, state ministries, Human capacity

**This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria**

Citation: Bamidele, F. and Olatunde, J.I. (2026). Evaluation of Human Capacity Development in Ondo State Building Construction Industry. *Continental J. Applied Sciences*, 21(1), 30-49. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18467526

Introduction

Background to the study

It is generally accepted that the construction industry is a significant sector of every nation's economy and plays a major role in the economic development of many nations. The construction industry builds the public and private infrastructure that provides the foundation for economic well-being development and improved standards of living. It is a vital sector of a nation's economy and there is a growing recognition that construction can be a more important source of employment generations. The effective operation of the construction industry is made possible by the availability of essential resources. These are materials, plants and equipment and human capacity resources. Human capacity refers to the stock of skills and knowledge embodied in the ability of people to perform labour so as to produce economic value. According to Huselid (1998) "human capacity is the skills and knowledge gained by a worker through education and training". Gibberd (2003), defined human capacity as "that which is acquired and useful abilities of all the inhabitants or members of the society. It can be acquired through formal schooling and on-the-job training. It is substitutable but not transferable (Opara, 2007).

A well-developed human capacity base of a nation plays an important role in its economic development. Human capacity development can be increased by investing in health care, education and job training. But a pertinent question is, do the investments in human capacity development felt in the industry especially as it concerns addressing the issue of collapse of buildings during and after construction? In the examination of the reasons for numerous structural collapses, Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions (1998), indicates that "in most cases, the failure was caused by human mistakes, events due to limitations of knowledge of structural behavior or unanticipated environment phenomena". It should be noted that notwithstanding the size and pace of human capacity investment, it will necessitate a fixed number of years to shape a generation of educated and skilled labour force, which will entail investments in human development to be meaningful, it should be sustained over a long period of time (Castanda-Maza, 2002). Human capacity represents the knowledge, skills and abilities that make it possible for people to do their jobs. Human capacity development is about recruiting, supporting and investing in people, using a variety of means, including education, training, coaching, mentoring, internship, organizational development and human resources management

**This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria**

Human capacity development is providing individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary not only to enter the labour market but also to maintain quality employment and is increasingly recognized as the most effective instrument to counter labour exclusion and economic polarization (Huselid, 1998).

According to Opara (2007) the development of human capacity should be an important agenda of the government to produce a highly skilled and competitive workforce, locally and internationally. The strategy to develop a qualitative human capacity depends, among others, on two main factors, that is, enhancing industry is important not only in housing production but in the general infrastructure development of the country and more importantly in its ability to generate employment and stimulate national development. The construction industry in Nigeria has contributed immensely to the national development

Statement of the Problem

In the recent time, the problems being faced by poor human capacity building in the built environment are as follow: desegregation and diversification of the progressive movement, lack of platform to facilitate innovation and lack of shared definitions and shared languages e.tc. These have caused a lot of problems in the construction industry as stated bellow.

A well-developed human capacity base of a country, play an important role in the economic development of a nation. The development of a skilled labour force makes an important contribution to development. According to Obiegbu (2002), "skilled workers (craftsmen and artisans) and technicians enhance the quality and efficiency of product development, production and maintenance and they also help train workers of lesser skills".

Recently, the Nigerian construction industry and specifically, the building industry seem to have been plagued with collapse of building with resultant calamities. Many states of the federation have recorded at least one building collapse in a year. Building collapse has been recorded in major cities of Nigeria especially Lagos, Ibadan, Osogbo, Ado-Ekiti and Akure. When building collapse, many lives are lost and are being lost on daily basis as a result of collapse of existing or building under construction. According to Emeka (2014), not less than 120 people died in one of the churches which collapsed at ikotun-Egbe area of Lagos with one more than 100 people seriously injured. Also, Chioma (2014), reported that on the 8th of May, 2014 a building collapsed, killing not less than three people in Sango, along Akure-Ado road; Akure.

Various commissions of enquiry have been set up to unravel the mystery of building collapse in Nigeria. One of the main causes of building collapse is the human resource employed in the construction industry. According to Opara (2007), the examination of the reasons for numerous structural collapses indicate that in most cases, the failures were caused by human mistakes. Based on this general problem, the research has these gaps to identify other problems. These include; lack of training and continuous education for the professionals and the contractors, non-availability of funds in training the professionals and so on. The quality of human capacity employed to carry out work at different stages of the construction projects is very important both in terms of safety and economic development of the nation.

Research Question

1. what human capacity development approach is used to develop the building construction staff in the study area?
2. what are the challenges of human capacity development facing by the ondo state construction industry?
3. which human capacity development method is preferred by the professionals?
4. Does the human capacity used meet with modern trend in the building construction
5. Does this method preferred met with the modern trend?

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The goal of the study is to evaluate human capacity development in ondo state building construction industry. The specific objectives are to:

1. assess the human capacity development approach used to develop the building construction staff in the study area;
2. examine the challenges faced by the ondo state construction industry,
3. identify the human capacity development method preferred by the professional
4. to examine this method preferred vis as vis the modern trend in the construction Industry?

Significance of the study

The significance and the benefits of the research as stated: increase employee satisfaction, improve retention rates, develop employee engagement and develop client engagement. The role of human capacity development is the key to economic development of a nation. Everyone needs to be developed for productivity, capacity development is dynamic. One of the greatest assets of the industry is the human resources available. There are many research work on major causes of building

collapse, success factors while some studies focused on effects of building collapse on building construction industry. However, it appears that there is no previous work on evaluation of human capacity development in Ondo State building construction industry. This gap in the research has motivated the study. The study is intended to bring lasting solution to the problems of developing human capacity. This research work will help the government to identify the factors that contribute to the challenges faced by the Ondo State construction industry in developing building construction professionals in order to bring a lasting solution to the problem of poor output and collapse of building in the State. Also, it will increase the interest of government in training and developing the professionals in other to achieve the organizational goal. The findings of this research will be of immense benefit to the professional bodies, the relevant building authority, building contractors and other researchers.

Scope of the study

The study covered the evaluation of human capacity development in Ondo State building industry. The study area for this research was Ondo State and collection of data will be limited to Ondo State only.

Limitations of the Study

The research work was faced by the following limitations that were appropriately managed in other to enhance the validity of the research findings. Confidentiality of information, The organizations visited were trying to keep some information. Counter biasing questions were used to get confidential information about the organizations. Some respondents lacked understanding on crucial aspects of the study. The researcher explained the questions to the respondents so that they know exactly what is expected from them.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design was based on survey method which accommodates the use of questionnaire to elicit information from the respondents involved in the study area. Questionnaire was subsequently designed as the main research instrument in elicit information from the professionals in the Ministry of Works, Ministry of Housing and Urban Development and Contractors within the study areas.

Study Area

The study area research was Ondo State, Nigeria. Ondo State (Sunshine State) was created on February 3, 1976, is one of the 36 States of the federation of Nigeria, made up of 18 Local Government Areas. Ondo State is located in the Southwestern Zone of

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria

Nigeria. The land area is approximately 14,788.723 Square kilometers is bounded in the North by Ekiti and Kogi States; in the East by Edo state; in the West by Osun and Ogun states and in the South by the Atlantic Ocean.

Population of the Study

The population of this study was made up of the professionals and the contractors in the Firms and Sites visited. The study population was obtained from the administrative department of these firms The total population was one hundred and eighty nine (189) professionals and contractors

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

The sample used in the study was selected using purposive sampling which is a non-probability sampling technique. Under purposive sampling techniques, the researchers chose who in her opinion are thought to be relevant to the research, the judgement of the researcher was more important in selecting the respondents. A fact finding was done, by visiting the required Firms and Sites in the study area. The population of the professionals and the contractors was 189, the researchers purposively selected professionals and contractors both in the Firms and on the Sites; therefore the total sample sizes consists of 98 respondents. This population (189) was obtained from the administrative department of the Firms and on the Sites. The required respondents were determined by using Yamane's Statistical Distribution Formula (1967).

Method of data collection

A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data. Journals and reports were used for collection of secondary data. The questionnaire was personally administered to the respondents in order to prevent loss in transit and to be rest assured that they were adequately filled, the researcher used time to familiarize with the respondents in order to educate them on the need to give maximum cooperation.

Study Variables and their measurements

The study variables for the study were measured as follow:-

- i. Human capacity development approach used to develop building construction staff: very low (1), low (2), moderate (3), high (4), very high (5).
- ii. Challenges faced by the construction industry in developing their professionals: very low (1), low (2), moderate (3), high (4), very high (5).
- iii. Human capacity development methods preferred by the professionals: very low (1), low (2), moderate (3), high (4), very high (5)

Research Instrument

The instrument used for this study was questionnaire. Copies of questionnaire were used to elicit information on the objectives of the study. The questionnaire was designed into section A, B, C and D. Section A relates to demographic characteristics of the respondent while section B, C, and D deals with the real question concerning staff in the study area, Challenges faced by the Ondo State construction industry in developing their workmen method preferred by the professionals.

Content Validity

The instrument was given to experts in construction industry for critical examination and criticism, their comments were used to make necessary amendments on the question drawn in measuring the variables.

Validation of Instruments

The questionnaire was validated through a pilot study that was carried out on a least five professionals (1. e Builders, Architect, Structural Engineer, Estate Surveyor and Quantity Surveyor) and some contractors in charge of building construction projects in some Organizations/Firms in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The result showed that the validation was adequate.

Method of Data analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze data collection from the field Descriptive Statistic used includes, Percentage, frequency distribution, severity index, mean and standard deviation. While the inferential statistic were used was analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables. The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) is used to determine whether there are any significant differences between the means of three or more independent (unrelated) groups.

Where;

X = individual observation

R= number of groups

N=total number of observations (all groups)

N= number of observations in group

Results and Discussion

Response Rate of response to questionnaire

Table 1 showed the total number of questionnaire administered were ninety-eight (98), out of which ninety-two (92) were properly filled by the professionals and contractors in ondo state construction industry. From the study, ninety-two (92) of

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria

the targeted respondents filled the questionnaire making a response rate of 93.9%. The numbers of the returned questionnaires were certified satisfactory for the purpose of the analysis and statistically tested to be reliable and valid. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) observed that 50% response rate is adequate, 60% and above is good, 80% rated is very good. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire and waited for respondents to fill in, and picked once fully completed. The response rate demonstrates a willingness of the respondents to participate in the study

Table 1: Response rate

Response rate	Constructed Sites	Constructed Firms	
Total			
No distributed	40	58	98
No received and used	38	54	92
Percentage	95.5%	93.15	93.9%

Source: field survey (2020)

Demographic Information Respondents

Table 2 shows the personal information of the respondents in terms of their profession, qualification, professional status and professional regulatory council. The first information that was measured is the profession of the respondents which is shown in table 2. It is revealed that, a larger percentage of 19.5 of the respondents whose opinions were sampled were Quantity Surveyors. The table also shows that 18.5 were Engineers, so also Estate Surveyors (18.5), while 16.3% were town planners. The table reveals that 10.9% were architects, while 8.7% were builders. The table also shows that 5.4% were site engineers while other professionals were 2.5%. the table shows that the quantity surveyors have highest number among the professionals in the ministries. This is followed by the Engineers and Estate Surveyors who have same number of professional status, the town planners are also many in number followed by the architects. The builders and the site Engineers has the lowest number of professional status. This implies that among different professions in Ondo State construction industry, there are more quantity surveyors among other professions that form building team like architect, Builders, Site Engineer are very few in the ministries. This is a clear indication that output of building construction is affected in the state.

Table 2 shows the qualification of the respondents. It shows that 32.6% of the respondents were MSc/M.Tech holders which were the majority of the respondents. It is clear indication that a larger percentage of the respondents are well able to

provide valid information for the purpose of this study based on their level of academic. Followed by 30.4% of respondents which were HND holders, 25.0% were B.Sc. holders, while 6.5% were ND holders and 5.4% of the respondents possessed other form of educational qualifications different from the ones mentioned above. It was also observed from the Table 2 that among the different qualifications of the respondents in the industry, M.Sc. Holders were more than others at that time this research project has been carried out. It implies that there is need for more technically trained human capacity to work with the managerial human capacity to manage the various construction works effectively.

Table 2 shows that, majority of the respondents in the two ministries are not yet registered with any of the professional association 60%, while 32.4% of the respondents were qualified as corporate members. Associate members (5.4%), 2.2% were Graduate members in their various professions. This could be deduced that there is a low performance record of the construction professional bodies in the industry. It suggests that there are construction works that are managed by individuals who are not yet registered professionals. Therefore, cases of building collapses in ondo state could be connected to the activities or involvement of those who are not yet registered with their various professional bodies. The above scenario in the nation's capacity does not show any serious human capacity development in the construction industry in Ondo State and in Nigeria as a whole.

In Table 2, it shows that not all the respondents are registered members of their professional association. Among the different professional regulatory council of the respondents, those who do not belong to any professional regulatory council have the highest percentage of the respondents (60.0%), this is followed by QSRBN (7.6%), also 7.6% respondents has COREN, and others also were 7.66, these respondents were those who have not completed their registration with the professional council were. While the respondents that have CORBON were 5.4%, ARCON and ESVRBON were 4.3% respectively.

Followed by TOPREC (3.2%) with the lowest percentage. The situation above tells that in the Ministries, there is little or no drive towards making their staff to be registered by any of these professional associations. This could suggest that, the issue of human capacity development among the different professions is taken with less seriousness.

Table 2: Demographic Information of Respondents

Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
Professionals		
Architect	10	10.9
Builder	8	8.9
Engineer	17	18.5
Quantity Surveyor	18	19.5
Estate Surveyor	17	18.5
Town Planner	15	16.3
Site Engineer	5	5.4
Others	2	2.5
Total	92	100.0
Qualifications		
M.sc/M.Tech	30	32.2
B.sc	23	25.0
HND	28	30.4
OND	6	6.5
OTHERS	5	5.4
TOTAL	92	100.0
Profession Status		
Corporate	30	32.4
Graduate	2	2.2
Associate	5	5.4
Others	55	60.0
Total	92	100.0
Professional regulatory councils		
ARCON	4	4.3
CORBON	5	5.4
COREN	7	7.6
QSRBN	7	7.6
TOPREC	3	3.2
ESVBON	4	4.3
OTHERS	7	7.6
NONE	55	60.0
TOTAL	92	100.0

Source: field survey 2020

Human Capacity Development Approach used to develop Building Construction staff in the study area.

Table 3 shows the mean values of the respondent ranges between 3.9 and 3.4. among the factors, formulation of sustainable human capacity policy was rated high with the mean score council on human capacity development with the mean score of 3.8. however, provision of fund for training and educating construction professionals were rated 3.6.introducing compulsory continuous professional skills (3.6).while creating market for sustainability was rated 3.5 and introducing internship training which was 3.4 were rated 3.5 and introducing internship training which were rated low by the respondents.

The result confirms UNDP (2010) observation that, without supportive strategies, policies, educated and skilled staff, organization lack the foundation to plan, implement and review their development strategies. Also, that capacity development helps to strengthen and sustain this foundation. Hildebrand and Grindle (1994) also concurred with the findings that, policies to guide organizational work must be well designed for the organization to work efficiently, because the policies have a significant impact on staff performance, and should be developed in line with human capacity development outcomes. Kalemci (2005) explained about the importance of training, that provision must be made for fund in training and developing human capacity because it is tremendously important in the effective management and maintenance of a skilled workforce. According to Aguinis et. al., (2009), organization should commit itself to the progress of training by introducing continuous professional skills so as to improve their knowledge or skill to carry out their professional job efficiently and effectively for better result in achieving organizational goal. UNDP (2011), observed that opportunity for continued learning, through access to professional training for example, are an essential non-monetary incentive for retaining staff within an organization

Table 3: Human Capacity Development approach used to Develop Building Construction Staff in the area

Factors	Mean Rating
Sustainable human capital policy	3.90
Construction's professional stakeholders adversary council on human capital	3.64
Training and educational program skills	3.57
Creating market for sustainability	3.49
Internship training	3.40
Provision of various type of incentive to the staff	3.57
Provision of seminar within and outside the state/country	3.52
Health scheme system	3.26

Field survey 2015 Key: Very low 1, Low 2, Moderate 3, High 4, Very high 5

Means with the same letters along the same column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria

Challenges faced by the Ondo State Construction Industry in Developing Professionals.

Challenges faced by the Ondo State construction industry in developing professionals is shown in Table 4 among all these factors, financial problem (4.03) was rated highly as the most important barrier to training and developing staff in the industry. Three among the factors were rated above average, the factors were, lack of imparting training on newly recruited staff (3.60), taking too long to implement the training process (3.58) and lack of proper organization for the workplace of the training (3.36) while five were rated below average, the factors were, lack of appraisal in order to motivate the employees to attend training (3.29), non-availability of skilled trainer (3.27) lack of skills that the trainer should possess to make the training effective (3.21), it shows from the findings that, when trainers and trainees work together with positive and motivated bent of minds it will improve organizational health and quality of products with much less wastage of the resources leading to increased profitability. The society will get superior products at much lower costs. The improved and effective working style of the employees will in turn provide healthy and pollution free environment to the society. While lack of safety awareness (3.12) and lack of interest by the staff was rated 2.85. It can be deduced from the study that, financial problem is the most important barrier to training and developing staff and other factors is higher.

The finding conforms to Mamoria (1992) observation that, shortage of fund and inadequate facilities hamper effective and development programmes, which affects organization growth. Saks and Haccoun (2007) observed that lack of adequate financial resources for training and development of professionals means that functional and lasting organization cannot be provided resulting in half-baked semi-literate staff who are neither useful to themselves nor to the organization economically. Abdulhammed (2003) asserted that it is important that all newly recruited workers should undergo introduction training. This means proper introduction to their jobs as well as provide them with information about the organization, its rules and policies. According to Kalemci (2005) a workplace of the training must be conducive for the trainees and adequate information must be made to avoid creating problems for the organization. Aguinis et al. (2009), observed that, most significant thing about training is that if trainers have good knowledge, experience, confidence and the ability to motivate trainees then it brings out great results which helps the development of individual as well as organization. So for success training results there must be positive motivation, sometime training found more emotional intelligent. As a whole the understanding and implementation of the paper contents in letters and spirit, it will provide multifaceted benefits to the individuals, organizations and society as whole in the following manner, ie trainers

and trainees will be benefitted as due to increased clarity of training contents and improved training delivery the training effectiveness will be much more which will motivate both parties and learning will be long lasting. According to Muhwezi et al, (2012), when trainers and trainees work together with positive and motivated bent of mind it will improve organizational health and quality of products will much less wastage of the resources leading to increase in profit as well as good output.

Table 4 Challenges faced by the Ondo State Construction Industry in developing their Professionals

Factors Rating	Mean
Financial Problem	4.03
Lack of imparting training on newly recruited staff	3.60
Taking too long implement the trained process	3.58
Lack of proper organisation for the workplace of the training	3.36
Lack of appraiser in other to motivate the employees to attend training	3.29
Non availability of skilled trainer	3.27
Lack of skills that the trainer should process to make the training effective	3.21
Lack of safety awareness	3.12
Lack of interest by the staff	2.85

Means with the same letters along the same column are not significantly different at P0.05

Source: filed survey 2020 Key: very low-1Low-2 Moderate-3High-4Very high-5

Human Capacity Development Method preferred by the Professionals

The human capacity development method preferred by the professionals is shown in Table 5 among the methods, professional training is more preferred by the professionals, it is rated higher than every other methods with mean rating of 4.38. This is followed by continuous education with mean rating 4.12. While, seminar within and outside the state is rated 3.88 so also. On the job training is rated 3.88. internship training for young graduates is rated 3.79, workshop training programme for all cadres is rated 3.70, continuous professional and skills development with mean rating of 3.68 and management training has the mean rate of 3.60.

These showed that Professional training plays great role in the total development of the professionals. The uses of different software that helps the professionals to perform and delivered their tasks at expected period of time are introduced during course of the training. Project management software has become a fundamental way for organizations to optimize processes, ensuring that they offer the highest level of efficiency and effectiveness while carrying out projects throughout the company.

Project management software is one of the most helpful tools that can assist professionals in being as effective as positive.

Training is crucial for organizational development and its success which is indeed fruitful to both employers and employees of an organization. World Bank policy paper (1991) concur that professional training and development are part of good management practices and good risk management strategies in developing professionals in construction industry. Training and development are used together to bring about the overall acclimation, improvement, and education of an organization's employees.

Training and development increases productivity, develop skills, less supervision and gives job satisfaction (Smith and Mazin, 2004).

Table 5: Human Capacity Development Method preferred by the Professionals

Factors Rating	Mean
Professional training	4.38
Continuous education	4.12
Seminar (within and outside the state)	3.88
On the job training	3.88
Internship training for young graduates	3.79
Workshop training programme for all cadres	3.70
Continuous professional and skills development	3.68
Management training	3.60

Source: field survey 2020

Key: very low-1, Low-2, Moderate-3, High-4, Very high-5, Means with the same letters along the same column are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$

Conclusion

The construction industry builds the public and private infrastructure that provides the foundation for economic well-being/development and improved standards of living. Therefore, more importance must be attached to the growth of the industry. Among all the factors that contribute to the success of any organization, human capacity development in terms of training plays a vital role. Since it is the people that will put the other resources to work, it should be viewed as such by management, by giving it due attention in order to achieve its organizational goals and objectives. Human capacity development aimed at ensuring that the right person is available for the right job at the right time. This involves formulating a

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria

forward looking plan to ensure that the necessary human effort to make it possible for the survival and growth of the organization becomes imperative to develop the employee. Training has come to the regards as a vital tool of management capable of making important contribution to the goals of the organization. Training attempts to improve the performance of the employees and organization by closing the gap between expectations and achievements.

Time and money spent on training and development in the future of the ministry, recognizing that employees are an organizational most important asset. The instruction of compulsory continuous professional skills development and education for all cadres of construction workers will have great impact in achieving sustainable human capacity development in the ministries and in the construction industry as a whole. Employer's relationship with their employees has to be nurtured and taken care of in order to be beneficial for both individuals; their co-workers, and the organization as a whole. It has long been noted that strong employer-employee relationships often lead to greater employee happiness and significantly improved in productivity.

Recommendations

The following recommendation were made arising from the research findings,

- a. The government should introduce professional training and continuous education for the professionals in the study area, for effective human capacity development in other to achieve a desired output of building constructions.
- b. The various professional regulatory bodies should encourage the professionals to register their membership, as this will checkmate the activities and involvement of the quacks in the building industry.
2. The government should provide adequate funds for training and continuous education in development the workmen, since the requirements of human capacity development in construction industry demands new skills and continuous learning.
3. Government or a coalition of the relevant regulatory bodies should convene advisory stakeholder council that can formulate guidelines for sustainable construction, liaise with other sectors and advise government regarding appropriate policy.
4. Introduction of orientation programme for the newly employed staff. The newly developed staff should be oriented to have interest in developing themselves in terms of training and continuous education.

Contribution to knowledge

The research has contributed the followings to knowledge;

The study showed the level of human capacity development in the construction industry and has also enabled a better understanding of why the country will still have to cope with the menace of building collapse for some time to come. It has showed that effective competitive advantage through people is the ultimate goal of human capacity development. The study has helped in identifying the needs for training and continuous education of construction workers and the strategy that could be adopted to enhance the skills.

References

- Abdulhammed, A.S. (2003). Training and on-the-job acquisition for builders, a paper Presented at the annual conference of the Nigerian institute of building with the Centre for women development, Abuja, 13th September, 2003.
- Aguinis, herman and kraiger, k. (2009). "benefits of training and development for Individuals, teams, organizations and society", annual review of psychology, 60(4)
- Castanda-Mada, J. (2002). Workers' skills and receptiveness to operate under the tier II Construction Management Strategy. PhD. Thesis. Univ. of Texas at Austin, Austin.
- Chioma Gabriel, (2014). Building Collapse in Akure. Available online at <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/05/2-die-3-injured-building-collapses-Akure>.
- Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions (DETR) (1998). Sustainable construction: sustainable development: opportunities for Change, department of the environment, transport and the Region (DETR).
- Emeka Obi, (2014). The 2014 Synagogue Church Building Collapse https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2014_synagogue_church_building_collapse available online.
- Gibberd, J. (2003). Building systems to support sustainable development in developing Countries, facilities planning and management. CSIR Building and Construction technology. Pretoria.

- Haselid, M. (1998). The impact of human resource management practices on turnover, Productivity, and corporate financial performance. Strategic human Resources management: A reader Mabey, C., Salam, G., and storey, J. eds., Sage Publications, London.
- Hilderbrand, M. E. and Grindle, M. S. (1994). Building Sustainable Capacity: Challenges for the Public Sector, Harvard Institute for International Development, Cambridge, MA.
- Kalemci, P. (2005). "general overview of training effectiveness and measurement Models", Journal of Commerce & Tourism Education Faculty, 1(2005), pp.144-156.
- Kaiser, N., & Barstow, C. K. (2022). Rural Transportation Infrastructure in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Review of Impacts, Implications, and Interventions. *Sustainability*, 14(4), 2149. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042149>
- Mamoria, C. B. (1992). Personnel Management. Bombay: Himalaya Pub. House.
- Mugenda, O. M & Mugenda, A. G. (2003). Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches. Nairobi: Acts Press.
- Muhwezi, L., Chamuriho, L.M. and Lema, N.M. (2012). An Investigation into Materials Wastes on Building Construction projects in Kampala-Uganda. Scholarly Journal of Engineering Research, 1(1), 11-18.
- Obiegbu, L.Y. (2002), Materials Management on Sites. B.Sc. Thesis submitted to the Department of Surveying, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.
- Saks, A.M. and Haccoun, R.R. (2007). Managing performance through training and development. Toronto : Thomson Nelson.
- Smith, S.P. and Mazin, R.A. (2004). The HR answer book: An indispensable guide for managers and human resources professionals.
- UNDP (2010). "Human Development Report 2010". Oxford University Press, New York.

UNDP (2011). The HDI 2010. New controversies, old critiques. Eds Klugman et al. United Nations Development Programme Human Development Reports Research Paper 2011/01.

World Bank. 1991. World Development Report 1991: The Challenge of Development. © World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/5974>.
<https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-1952-0868-9>

Yamane, Y. (1967). Mathematical formulae for sample size determination (2nd ed.). Harper and Row.

CITY UNIVERSITY OF CAMBODIA
SCHOOL OF MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGY
DEPARTMENT OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGY
Questionnaire of research project:

EFFECT OF HUMAN CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT ON OUTPUT OF BUILDING CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

Note: Any information given is purely for academic purpose, and will be treated Confidentially

Thanks for your cooperation

Section A: (characteristic of the Respondents)

1. Name of organization.....
2. What is your profession:.....
Architect Builder Engineer Quantity Surveyor Land Surveyor
Estate Surveyor Town Planner Contractor Site Engineer
Others, please indicate.....
3. What is your highest educational qualification
B.sc M.sc PhD. OND HND NBTE
Others, please specify.....
4. What is your professional status?
Fellow Corporate Graduate Associate others, please
indicate.....
5. Which of the professional regulatory council/board do you registered with?
6. ARCON CORBON COREN QSRBN

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria

7. TOPREC ESVRBON OTHERS NONE

Section B; Human Capacity Development approach used to develop the Building Construction Staff in the State

Please tick () the option that are appropriate for the answers to the question below.

1-Very low, 2-low, 3-Moderate, 4-Hihg, 5-Very High

Factor	1	2	3	4	5
Formulation of sustainable human capital development policy					
Creation of construction professional's stake holders adversary council on human capital development					
Provision of fund for training and educating construction professionals					
Training and education programme					
Provision of seminar within and outside the state/country					
Internship training for youth graduates in all fields and construction					
Health scheme system					
Compulsory continuous professional skills development and education programme for all cadres of construction workers					
Provision of various types of incentive to the staff					
Market for sustainability construction professionals					

To what extent do the following factors contribute to human capacity development approach used to develop the building construction staff in the study area

Section c: challenges faced by the construction firms in developing their professionals

To what extent do the following factors contribute to the challenges facing construction firms in developing professionals?

Factor	1	2	3	4	5

**This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License
ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and EducationDevelopment Inst., Nigeria**

Financial problem is the most important barrier to training and developing staff in your organization					
Non availability of skilled trainer					
Lack of interest by the staff					
Lack of appraisal in order to motivate the employees to attend training					
Taking too long to implement the training process					
Lack of imparting training on newly recruited staff					
Lack of proper organization for the workplace of the training					
Lack of the skills that the trainer should possess to make to training effective					
Lack of safety awareness					

Section D: Human capacity development method preferred by the professionals.

To what extent do the following methods preferred by the professionals?

Factor	1	2	3	4	5
Professional training					
Continuous education					
Seminar(within and outside the state)					
On-the-job training					
Internship training for young graduates					
Workshop training programs for the cadres					
Continuous professionals and skills development					
Management training					